

Research Yourself: Analysing the effects of Coaching Psychology among doctoral candidates

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Abstract

Recent research has shown the effectiveness of Coaching Psychology interventions as a valuable approach to support doctoral candidates' wellbeing and performance. One of the most studied constructs regarding the cognitive mechanisms by which coaching facilitates performance at the workplace is self-efficacy, but, to date, it has not been explored yet among research careers. Accordingly, the present study aimed to implement, for the first time in Spain, a coaching-psychology intervention among doctoral candidates and to assess changes in self-efficacy before and after the intervention. 20 doctoral candidates at the University of Barcelona participated in the study and were randomly assigned to 6 individual or group-format weekly sessions. Results showed very large increases in self-efficacy after the coaching sessions, independent of the intervention format (group or individual). Although further studies are needed, the present results encourage more research on the topic and suggest that coaching psychology would be an effective strategy for universities to increase

early-stage researchers' self-efficacy and, potentially, to better cope with the increasing mental health problems after the Covid-19 pandemic among doctoral candidates.

Keywords: doctoral candidates, early-stage researchers, self-efficacy, self-awareness coaching outcome, wellbeing, talent development.

Introduction

Recent research has shown the effectiveness of workplace coaching as a valuable approach to support individuals processes both in educational contexts in general (Andreannof, 2016; Bozer & Jones, 2018; Griffiths 2005) and in doctoral education in particular (Kearns, Gardiner, & Marshall 2008; Geber, 2010; Lane & Wilde, 2018; McCarthy 2012). Coaching is considered a learning and development approach that places the learner at the centre of the learning experience (Smither, 2011). Griffiths (2005) distinguishes coaching from other helping or teaching roles, including both teaching and therapy, by stating that a key characteristic of coaching is a dialectic process of reflection towards the achievement of specific goals and a commitment to planned action in a specific performance area. However, compared to the widespread use of coaching in other workplaces and organisations, the presence of the coaching approach in higher education research is relatively new and although several institutions are currently offering coaching for doctoral students (Borthwick & Wissler, 2003; Kearns et al, 2008), research is just beginning to emerge. Empirical reports have recently shown that early-stage researchers (ESR) and young academic staff are a risk population to develop stress-related disorders, and it is suggested that ESRs' mental health demands urgent attention after the Covid-19 pandemic (Byrom, 2020; Byrom et al., 2020; Cheng & Song, 2020; Cladellas et al., 2018; Johnson et al., 2020; Levecque et al., 2017; Suart, Suart & Graham, 2020; WHO, 2020; Wolston, 2019). This situation is

found in different European Universities, as several internal quality assessment reports show (University of Gröningen, 2018; Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2019). Accordingly, the European Charter for Researchers (European Commission, 2011) or the European Council of Doctoral Candidates (EURODOC; Kismihók, et al., 2019) recommend that Higher Education institutions should urgently develop methods and services for ESR's career management, such as coaching programmes, in order to provide adequate support to guarantee researchers' wellbeing at their workplace and to foster their talent development. The coaching approach in higher education is mainly facilitative, with coaches having specialist knowledge on research career which is used to enable students identify actions to address the challenges they face (Morales et al. 2016). In this line, some studies provide evidence that coaching has a positive impact on academic staff within higher education to enhance academic staff career advancement, scholarly confidence, collaborative work, skills development or action planning (Roofe & Miller, 2015). However, there is limited research on the impact of coaching doctoral students specifically (McCarthy, 2012). The few studies that have explored the effectiveness of coaching in doctoral education have reported that students improve their abilities to manage their time, their self-expectations or their communication skills. These behaviours, in turn, are associated with lower stress, higher completion of their doctoral studies and higher emotional and personal wellbeing (Godskensen & Kobayashi, 2016; Kearns et al., 2008; Lane & Wilde, 2018). It was also reported that for those students who had thought about quitting their doctoral programme, coaching had influenced them to stay. Qualitative results highlight that coaching facilitates doctoral candidates to enable action, increase self-confidence and improve personal effectiveness. On the other hand, it is claimed that coaching accelerates research productivity in higher education, as it has been reported in a study

at the University of Witwatersrand, South Africa (Geber, 2010). This study demonstrated that coaching improved student-supervisor partnerships, increased participant self-awareness and contributed towards career progression, and attributed to the coaching programme an increase in tangible research outcomes, such as number of research publications, completion of research milestones and successful grant applications.

According to Bozer and Jones (2018), the cognitive mechanism that is mainly enhanced in a coaching process, and that might mediate the observed behavioural improvements, is self-efficacy, a construct that it has not been explored yet in doctoral contexts. Self-efficacy has received an important focus of attention from literature in the wider educational context, since social cognitive theory highlights self-efficacy as a central mechanism with a wide explanatory power on behavioural outcomes (Bandura, 1982; Bandura, 1986; Bandura et al., 1996). Research on self-efficacy indicates that individuals higher in self-efficacy set more challenging goals than those with lower self-efficacy and it has been shown that it is directly related to job satisfaction, greater attention and efforts to overcome failure and to succeed in work-related performance (Judge & Bono, 2001; Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998). Furthermore, it has been reported that self-efficacy is a strong predictor of motivation, engagement behaviour and performance (Choi, Price, & Vinokur, 2003; Tannenbaum, Mathieu, Salas, & Cannon-Bowers, 1991). Self-efficacy has also been found to be related to improved self-awareness and responsibility, improved self-reported job performance (Bozer, Sarros, & Santora, 2013), and transformational leadership (MacKie, 2015) and it is considered as an important coaching outcome (Baron, Morin, & Morin, 2011; Grant, 2014; Grant, 2017; Moen & Federici, 2012; Tooth, Nielsen, & Armstrong, 2013). Accordingly, it is suggested that the study of self-efficacy in coaching studies is an

urgent priority given its relevance in all educational processes and its associations in performance and wellbeing outcomes (Bozer & Jones, 2018).

Accordingly, the aim of the present study was twofold. On the one hand, it aimed to implement, for the first time, an intervention based on Coaching Psychology in Spanish Doctoral Studies (Consejo General de Psicología de España, 2014; Reche et al., 2014). On the other hand, it aimed to assess, also for the first time in doctoral settings, to what extent this intervention improved self-efficacy, considered a central cognitive mechanism by which coaching mediates behavioural performance and wellbeing among doctoral candidates. Therefore, based on previous studies, it was hypothesized that participants of the coaching programme would increase their self-efficacy after the coaching process.

Method

Design and procedure

A pre-post study was designed to analyse the coaching intervention effectiveness in doctoral students' self-efficacy. To recruit participants, researchers called the intervention "Research Yourself" and chose randomly one of the 8 Universities located in Barcelona city and surroundings. The final university that was chosen was the University of Barcelona. Researchers contacted the doctoral school managers by email and explained the aim and design of the study and offered the coaching intervention for free to the university as a pilot study. The managers and ethical committee of the university approved the protocol and PhD students from University of Barcelona were recruited via email. Participants were informed that their participation would be

voluntary and that the treatment of their data would be anonymous and would not be used by their supervisors or research staffs. In this email, doctorate students were invited firstly to assist to an informative session where contents and timing of the Coaching Program were summarized. Finally, this kick-off session had 80 assistants (verified by signature). Twenty PhD's students from these 80 were selected for participating in the Coaching Program and the pre-post pilot study. The criteria selection was attendance to the kick-off session and accepting to receive pilot coaching sessions. In addition, as inclusion criteria, it was also taken into account candidates' explicit commitment to the coaching process and their perceived need for a change measure with a minimum of 8/10 points answering two questions 1) How do you think it is necessary for you to make a change in the way you are coping your doctorate? and 2) Level of commitment on participating in a coaching process working with a psychologist-coach at University of Barcelona Alumni Headquarters 1 session of 1 hour fortnightly. Applying this selection criteria, the participants were reduced to 34 doctoral students and a final sample of 20 students finally committed to Coaching Program timing. Participants were randomly assigned to group (n=10) or individual coaching (n=10). Both options consisted in 6 coaching sessions, but the former was delivered individually (one to one sessions) and the latter was delivered in a group. The sessions were conducted by four different coaches-psychologists offering 6 individual one-hour sessions duration for 10 PhD candidates and 6 coaching group sessions of one-hour and a half duration for the other 10 remaining candidates. Sessions took place in different classrooms and offices of Alumni Headquarters of University of Barcelona and in the Faculty of Philosophy at University of Barcelona. All participants consented to collaborate voluntarily and provided informed consent before participating in the study.

Coaches were selected through a voluntary call among trained psychologist at the Coaching Psychology Section of the Col·legi Oficial de Psicologia de Catalunya (COPC; Catalan Official Psychology Association).

Participants

20 Doctoral Candidates between 24 and 50 years old participated in the study, with a 75% of female representation. A 30% of participants were from Life-Science fields, another 30% of Social Sciences, followed by Humanities (20%), Health Sciences (15%) and Engineering (5%) (see Table 1).

Instruments

The Spanish version of the Self-Efficacy General Scale (SEGS; Schwarzer, 1993) was administered. This scale has been validated in different cultural backgrounds and it is considered a reliable tool for measuring self-efficacy in organizational research (Chen, Gully & Eden, 2001; Luszczynska, Scholz, Schwarzer, 2005). Self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977,1992) refers to the feeling of confidence in one's own abilities to properly manage daily life situations. People with low self-efficacy levels tend to show lower self-esteem and negative feelings on its capacity, while high self-efficacy facilitates positive thoughts related to oneself, acting these thoughts as motivators of action and facilitating self-esteem or the achievement of more challenging goals (Sanjuán Suárez, Pérez García, y Bermúdez Moreno, 2000). Cross-cultural studies have shown a good internal consistency (Sanjuán, Suárez, Pérez García y Bermúdez Moreno, 2000; Schwarzer, 1993) and the psychometric properties of the Spanish adaptation show similar results, with a high internal consistency and a considerable predictive value, which guarantee its usefulness in psychological studies about performance, health and educational

processes. Internal consistency for the present sample was also adequate, with Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.83$.

Statistical analyses

Means (standard deviations) and frequencies (percentages) were calculated for the socio-demographics. To analyse changes in self-efficacy after the intervention, the nonparametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used. Repeated-measures ANOVA was also performed to explore whether the format of coaching intervention (individual vs. group) had a differential effect on self-efficacy. A 5% significance level was adopted in all two-tailed tests. For a more precise interpretation on the relevance of the results in each assessed domain, effect sizes for pre-post changes were calculated using Cohen's d according to Morris and DeShon's (2002) equation (rule of thumb for Cohen's d : 0.2 = small, 0.5 = medium, and 0.8 = large effect sizes). Statistical analyses were conducted using the SPSS 25.0 statistical package.

Results

Sociodemographics are reported in Table 1. Statistically significant differences in self-efficacy were found in pre-post variations after the coaching intervention in both groups (see Table 2). Significant increases were observed in the total sample ($Z = -3.294$; $p = .000$), with a very large effect size ($d = 1.66$) and remained statistically significant after Bonferroni correction. No statistically significant difference regarding change in self-efficacy scores was found between the two types of intervention (individual vs. group) ($F = .633$; $p = .437$). Although not significant, larger effect sizes were obtained in group intervention ($d = 2.13$) while individual intervention showed a smaller but still large effect size ($d = 1.54$).

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of the participants.

Study sample (n= 20)	
<i>Sociodemographics</i>	
Gender	
Women	15 (75%)
Men	5 (25%)
Age, M (SD)	34.7 (7.25)
Working status	
<i>Working and PhD studying</i>	12 (60%)
<i>Only PhD studying</i>	8 (40%)
Area of study	
<i>Social Sciences</i>	6 (30%)
<i>Humanities</i>	4 (20%)
<i>Health Sciences</i>	3 (15%)
<i>Life Sciences</i>	6 (30%)
<i>Engineering and Architecture</i>	1 (5%)

Table 2. Pre-post changes in self-efficacy Scale.

	Pre Mean (SD)	Post Mean (SD)	Z	p-value	d
Individual sessions (n=10)	23.40 (9.18)	33.90 (2.80)	-2,809	.005	1.54
Group sessions (n=10)	27.30 (4.47)	35.10 (2.60)	-2,805	.005	2.13
All participants (n=20)	25.35 (7.30)	34.50 (2.70)	-3.294	.000	1.66

4. Discussion and conclusions

The aim of the present pilot study was to preliminarily analyse the effectiveness of a Coaching Psychology programme in terms of self-efficacy among doctoral candidates for the first time in a Spanish University. The present results show how participants in both coaching programmes -individual and group formats- experienced a statistically significant and large increase in self-efficacy scores after participating in the coaching programme, aligning with previous studies reporting the effectiveness of coaching in other workplace contexts (Bozer & Jones, 2018). Although the observed increase was

higher in the group intervention, differences regarding the individual intervention did not reach statistical significance, suggesting that both coaching modalities are equally effective. The present results might help behavioural researchers understand how coaching increases self-confidence, performance or personal effectiveness (Geber, 2010; Lane & Wilde, 2018). Self-efficacy increases observed in the present study might also help explaining the effectiveness of coaching in doctoral education, as a central cognitive mechanism that might facilitate individuals' abilities to manage self-expectations and personal goals towards wellbeing and performance. It could also help understanding previous results showing higher productivity, completion rates of doctoral studies and higher emotional and personal wellbeing in those students that go through a coaching process (Geber, 2010; Godskensen & Kobayashi, 2016; Kearns, Gardiner, & Marshall, 2008; Lane & Wilde, 2018). Therefore, and given the relevance of self-efficacy as a central cognitive mechanism in academic and professional performance (Bandura, 1986; Bozer & Jones, 2018), it is suggested that coaching psychology programmes -both individual and group- might be an effective psychoeducational intervention to increase academic motivation, engagement and performance (Choi, Price, & Vinokur, 2003; Judge & Bono, 2001; Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998; Tannenbaum, Mathieu, Salas, & Cannon-Bowers, 1991). Accordingly, results of this pilot study encourage more applied research of Coaching Psychology among doctoral studies to analyse its effects in academic motivation and in objective indicators of performance (Bozer, Sarros, & Santora, 2013).

Nevertheless, the present results should be interpreted with caution, since changes in self-efficacy do not necessarily be indicative of other short and long-term academic outcomes to be tested in further studies, such as stress levels, student-supervisor partnership, career progression or research outcomes such as number and quality of

publications (Geber, 2010; Lane & Wilde, 2016). Several limitations of the present study should be acknowledged: firstly, and the most important, the reduced sample size might be unrepresentative of general doctoral population and limits the generalizability of our findings. Secondly, the lack of control group makes impossible to draw meaningful conclusions from the study as an uncontrolled design impedes the possibility of attributing the observed beneficial effects of the coaching process in ESR's self-efficacy. On the other hand, it is necessary to highlight the fact that this study has only evidenced short-term transitory effects. Accordingly, more research should be carried using larger coaching programmes and measure the duration of these effects and their transfer to daily life in among doctoral students, including follow-up assessments.

In any case, this pilot study encourages the implementation and further research on the effectiveness coaching programmes among doctoral studies as an educational strategy to overcome the PhD crises (Cladellas et al., 2018; Wolston, 2019), worsened by the Covid-19 pandemic that has hardly hit Spanish and European universities and their ESRs. Accordingly, coaching programmes could help enhancing researchers' self-efficacy, and thus their psychological wellbeing and performance through cost-effective interventions, such as coaching-group sessions. This strategy could be a relevant teaching and learning innovation for those universities committed with their community and willing to foster researchers' talent development, upskill research staffs in wellbeing, avoid academic burnouts and doctoral withdrawals. Furthermore, it could be considered as a cost-effective psychoeducational strategy for mental health prevention among research staffs who are a risk population for developing stress-related disorders after the Covid-19 pandemic (Byrom, 2020; Byrom et al., 2020; Cheng &

Song, 2020; Cladellas et al., 2018; Johnson et al., 2020; Levecque et al., 2017; Suart, Suart & Graham, 2020; WHO, 2020; Wolston, 2019).

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